

COMPUTATIONAL DESIGN AND PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT OF MICROVASCULAR COMPOSITE PANELS FOR BATTERY COOLING

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Keywords: Gradient-based optimization, Interface-enriched generalized finite element method, Microvascular composites, Active cooling

ABSTRACT

Batteries for electric vehicles require active cooling to extend their lifespans and protect them from structural damage. To satisfy these requirements, conventional battery packaging consists of layers of aluminium to provided cooling and fiberglass to provide protection. With the goal of reducing weight while providing both cooling and superior damage protection, a new battery packaging scheme utilizing microvascular composite panels has recently been proposed. In these panels, complex 2D or 3D micro-channel networks can be embedded using a novel manufacturing technique based on a sacrificial fiber or template approach. Because most heat is dissipated via the coolant, the micro-channel design in the composite is crucial to the cooling performance of the panel. In this work, we develop a non-uniform rational B-spline (NURBS)-based interface-enriched generalized finite element method (IGFEM) for the thermal analysis of the composite. The thermal impact of the micro-channels is captured using a simplified model, which is validated with experiments and verified with FLUENT. By combining our IGFEM solver with a gradient-based optimization algorithm, we optimize the parallel channel design of various network topologies defined by the number of branches. A recently developed adjoint method and sensitivity analysis is applied to speed up the shape optimization. The optimal designs obtained using these techniques are shown to have superior performance to the reference network configurations.

1 INTRODUCTION

When operating at full capacity, car batteries generate a substantial amount of heat and must therefore be continuously cooled to avoid overheating and extend the lifespan of the batteries [1]. Current designs typically involve alternating aluminum and fiberglass layers placed between Li-ion battery packs. While an aluminum layer provides active cooling through a liquid circulating in its embedded channels, a fiberglass layer provides structural protection to the battery. To reduce the

weight of the cooling system while providing superior impact resistance, a novel battery packaging scheme using microvascular composite panels for both active cooling and structural protection of car batteries has been proposed [2]. Due to the lower thermal conductivity of carbon composite compared to aluminum, most heat generated by the battery has to be convected away by the coolant. Therefore, the design of the embedded channels is critical to the cooling performance of the panels. Fortunately, with recent advances in the manufacturing of microvascular composite components based on a sacrificial fiber or template approach [3, 4], we can now seamlessly embed a complex 2D or 3D network of micro-channels in the composite, thus allowing the enhancement of its cooling performance by optimizing its micro-channel design.

To design the microvascular composite panels, we develop a computational tool based on a NURBS-based interface-enriched finite element method (IGFEM) [5]. This allows for the efficient and accurate capture of the thermal impact of the embedded curved network of micro-channels using a simplified model with a finite element discretization that does not conform to the micro-channel geometry. The shapes of the embedded micro-channels are described by non-uniform rational b-splines (NURBS), which is a mathematical tool widely used in CAD to represent complex geometry [6]. We demonstrate the accuracy of the simplified model by validation with experiments and verification with more complex, 3D, coupled fluid/solid simulations performed with FLUENT.

Instead of performing a cumbersome parametric study to evaluate the performance of various micro-channel designs, we combine our IGFEM solver with a gradient-based optimization algorithm to optimize parallel designs, with the locations of the control points defining their geometry as design parameters. By employing an adjoint method and sensitivity analysis specially developed for IGFEM [7], we are able to perform the shape optimization efficiently for many design parameters starting from numerous initial designs. Through this process, we obtain optimal designs with substantially better performance than the reference designs. The shape optimization also highlights the key advantages of IGFEM, including the ability of the method to work with a fixed background mesh without the need to remesh to avoid severe mesh distortion as the channel geometry changes. Another key advantage is that only the nodal velocities of the enrichment nodes along the channels need to be calculated, thus limiting most of the computational work for sensitivity analysis to the enriched finite elements intersecting the channels.

2 METHOD

2.1 Simplified model

Figure 1: Geometry and boundary conditions of the model problem. The inset shows a portion of an unstructured non-conforming mesh

A microvascular composite is represented by a domain $\Omega = \Omega_s \cup \Gamma_f$ embedded with micro-channels Γ_f as shown in Figure 1. Because the micro-channel diameters are much smaller than the characteristic dimensions of the problem, we collapse the micro-channels into line sources/sinks. By applying energy conservation, the heat flow rate per unit length of a micro-channel is given by

$$q_l = \dot{m}_f c_f \frac{dT_m}{ds}, \quad (1)$$

where \dot{m}_f, c_f, s, T_m respectively denote the mass flow rate and the heat capacity of the coolant, the coordinate along the channel and the mixed-mean temperature [8] of the coolant. Let Γ_T and Γ_q be the parts of the boundary of Ω where Dirichlet and Neumann boundary conditions are specified, respectively and let us denote the thermal conductivity tensor of the solid, the unit tangent of Γ_f , the distributed heat source and the space of weighing function by $\boldsymbol{\kappa}, \hat{\boldsymbol{t}}, f$ and V , respectively. If we assume that the wall temperature of a channel approximately equals the mixed-mean temperature, we can write the weak formulation of the heat equation as

$$a(v, T) = (v, f) + (v, \bar{q})_{\Gamma_q}, \quad \forall v \in V, \quad (2)$$

where

$$a(v, T) = \int_{\Omega_s} \nabla v \cdot (\boldsymbol{\kappa} \nabla T) d\Omega + \int_{\Gamma_f} v c_f \dot{m}_f \hat{\boldsymbol{t}} \cdot \nabla T d\Gamma, \quad (3)$$

$$(v, f) = \int_{\Omega_s} v f d\Omega, \quad (4)$$

$$(v, \bar{q})_{\Gamma_q} = \int_{\Gamma_q} v \bar{q} d\Gamma. \quad (5)$$

The pressure drops and the flow rates in the channels can be obtained using the hydraulic equations for pipe networks as described in [9].

2.2 NURBS-Based IGFEM

Let the number of original nodes in the non-conforming mesh, a nodal value and its corresponding Lagrangian shape function be denoted by n_{on}, u_i and $N_i(\boldsymbol{x})$, respectively. In the IGFEM formulation [10], n_{en} enrichment nodes with generalized degrees of freedom β_j and enrichment functions $\psi_j(\boldsymbol{x})$ are added along the channels to yield the following expression for the finite element approximation:

$$T^h(\boldsymbol{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^{n_{on}} u_i N_i(\boldsymbol{x}) + \sum_{j=1}^{n_{en}} \beta_j \psi_j(\boldsymbol{x}). \quad (6)$$

If we let $[K], \{T\} = \{u_1, \dots, u_{n_{on}}, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_{n_{en}}\}, \{f\}$ respectively denote the global stiffness matrix, the vector of degrees of freedom and the load vector, the finite element discretization results in the system of equations $[K]\{T\} = \{F\}$. The IGFEM has been developed for polynomial [10] and NURBS [5, 11] enrichment functions. In Section 3.1, we demonstrate the convergence properties of the NURBS-based IGFEM compared to those of the standard FEM (SFEM).

2.3 Gradient-Based Optimization

Let $\boldsymbol{X}, \boldsymbol{d} = \{d_1, \dots, d_{n_d}\}'$, and \boldsymbol{g} respectively denote the nodal coordinates of the mesh, the design parameters and the nonlinear constraints. The general optimization problem takes the form

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\boldsymbol{d}} \theta(T(\boldsymbol{X}(\boldsymbol{d}), \boldsymbol{d}), \boldsymbol{X}, \boldsymbol{d}), \\ \text{subject to } \boldsymbol{g}(T(\boldsymbol{X}(\boldsymbol{d}), \boldsymbol{d}), \boldsymbol{X}, \boldsymbol{d}) \leq \mathbf{0}, \\ \text{and } [K]\{T\} = \{F\}, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where the last constraint arises from the finite element discretization.

The problem is solved using gradient-based optimization algorithms available in MATLAB. For efficiency, the derivative of the objective function θ with respect to a design parameter d_i is obtained analytically by applying the Reynolds transport theorem: If

$$\Phi(\mathbf{d}) = \int_{\Omega} \phi(T(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{d}), \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{d}) \, d\Omega, \quad (8)$$

the sensitivity is given by

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial d_i} = \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{D\phi}{Dd_i} + \phi \nabla \cdot \mathbf{V}^{(i)} \right) d\Omega, \quad i = 1, \dots, n_d, \quad (9)$$

which can be calculated efficiently using the adjoint method described in [7].

To extend the lifetime of the battery, we should keep the maximum temperature T_{max} low. However, T_{max} is not differentiable in the classical sense. Following standard practice in stress-based optimization [12], we use a differentiable alternative called the p -mean measure defined as

$$\theta = T_p = \left(\frac{1}{|\Omega|} \int_{\Omega} T^p \, d\Omega \right)^{1/p}. \quad (10)$$

The p -mean measure has the property: $\lim_{p \rightarrow \infty} T_p = T_{max}$. However, if p is too large, the problem becomes ill-conditioned or less smooth. On the other hand, small values of p may not allow T_p to capture the trend in T_{max} . Based on our numerical experience and recommended values in stress-based optimization [12], we adopt $p = 8$.

Figure 2: (a) Four-branch reference design, (b) four-branch random initial design, (c) seven-branch reference design and (d) seven-branch random initial design.

In this work, we optimize the parallel designs for different number of branches as shown in Fig. 2. The design parameters are the locations of the control points as indicated in blue excluding the inlet and outlet control points. As gradient-based optimization produces stationary solutions that may not be a global minimum, we perform the optimization starting from many distinct initial designs to increase our chance of obtaining solutions close to a global minimum. The initial designs, some of which are shown in Figures 2(b) and 2(d), have been generated by shuffling the control points randomly.

3 RESULTS

3.1 NURBS-Based IGFEM Convergence Study

We employ the method of manufactured solution to study the convergence rate and the accuracy of the NURBS-based IGFEM compared to SFEM. The study is carried out using the error in the L^2 -norm defined as

$$\|T - T^h\|_{L^2(\Omega)} = \sqrt{\int_{\Omega} (T - T^h)^2 \, d\Omega}. \quad (11)$$

In the study, a semicircular channel of radius r_o centered at $(L/2,0)$ with mass flow rate \dot{m} is embedded in a rectangular domain of conductivity κ as shown in Figure 3(a). The NURBS curve describing the semicircular channel can be found in [5]. Let $\alpha = \frac{\dot{m}c_f}{\kappa}$ and $\lambda = \frac{2k}{\alpha}$ for some $k > 0$. If we apply the following distributed heat source expressed in polar coordinates:

$$f(r, \phi) = \begin{cases} -(k^2 + \lambda^2)r_o^2 \left(\frac{r}{r_o}\right)^{k-2} e^{-\lambda\phi}, & r < r_o, \\ -(k^2 + \lambda^2)r_o^{-2} \left(\frac{r_o}{r}\right)^{k+2} e^{-\lambda\phi}, & r > r_o, \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

the thermal solution, shown in Figure 2(b), is

$$T(r, \phi) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{r}{r_o}\right)^k e^{-\lambda\phi}, & r < r_o, \\ \left(\frac{r_o}{r}\right)^k e^{-\lambda\phi}, & r > r_o. \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Figure 3: (a) Domain geometry for convergence study. (b) Analytical solution showing the presence of a gradient discontinuity in the temperature field along the semi-circular micro-channel.

Figure 4: Non-conforming (a,c) and conforming (b,d) meshes used in the convergence study.

Figure 5: L^2 -norm of the error versus (a) normalized mesh size and (b) degrees of freedom.

Some of the non-conforming and conforming meshes used in the study are shown in Figure 4. Setting $k = 3$ and $\alpha = 90$, we compare the errors of the IGFEM and the SFEM in Figure 5. As apparent in the figure, the IGFEM solution converges at a near optimal rate. For coarse mesh, the IGFEM solution is significantly more accurate compared to SFEM. However, for a given number of degrees of freedom, SFEM is slightly more accurate.

3.2 Validation and Verification

Figure 6: Experimental setup.

Experiments were performed on microvascular carbon fiber panels with the setup show in Figure 6. A carbon composite panel is heated from below by an electric heater. A water ethylene/glycol coolant is supplied by a peristaltic pump into the panel. The inlet temperature of the coolant is measured with a thermocouple reader and the temperature distribution of the panel is measured by an IR camera.

Figure 7: (a) FLUENT and (b) IGFEM setups with $L_x=0.15$ m and $L_y=0.2$ m.

We perform a 3D simulation of the panel in FLUENT with the conditions shown in Figure 7 (a) representative of those in experiments. A nonuniform heat flux $f(x)$ is applied at the bottom large face of the panel while convective and radiative heat losses are allowed from the top large face. The remaining smaller faces are insulated. As a comparison, we also perform a 2D IGFEM simulation with a nonuniform heat source $f(x)$ and heat loss allowed from the plane as shown in Figure 7(b). The edges of the plane are insulated except at the inlet where the temperature T_{in} is specified.

Figure 8: (a) Experiment and (b) FLUENT top surface temperature distributions and (c) IGFEM temperature distribution.

Figure 8 shows a good agreement between experimental, FLUENT and IGFEM temperature distributions for a spiral design. The average temperatures from experiment, FLUENT and IGFEM are 29.9°C, 28.4°C and 28.2°C, respectively. In the same order, the maximum temperatures are 33.0°C, 31.5°C and 31.4°C. Furthermore, the pressure drops are 125 kPa, 129 kPa and 106 kPa for experiment, FLUENT and IGFEM, respectively. The simulation results match with those of experiments within the uncertainty of the measurements.

3.3 Optimization

Figure 9: (a) Temperature distribution of the reference four-branch parallel design. (b) Optimal four-branch parallel design with its temperature distribution (c).

Figure 10: (a) Temperature distribution of the reference seven-branch parallel design. (b) Optimal seven-branch parallel design with its temperature distribution (c).

Using the IGFEM and sensitivity analysis, we optimize the parallel designs with four and seven branches. Figures 9(a) and 10(a) show the temperature distributions of the reference designs for these two cases. For lower number of branches, the optimal design tends to have vertically orientated interior channels as evident in Figure 9(b). However, for higher number of branches, the orientation of the interior channels in the optimal design tends to be diagonal as shown in Figure 10(b). The comparison of the temperature distributions in Figures 9(a), 9(c), 10(a) and 10(c) clearly shows that the non-uniformity of the temperature has been substantially reduced. Moreover, the maximum temperatures have been lowered by about 5°C.

4 CONCLUSIONS

An efficient and accurate simplified model for the thermal analysis of microvascular composites has been validated with experiments and validated with FLUENT. The temperature distribution is obtained using the NURBS-based IGFEM that is able to handle the geometry of curved micro-channels described by NURBS exactly, without the need for a conforming mesh. As demonstrated in a convergence study involving a semi-circular micro-channel, the convergence and accuracy properties of NURBS-based IGFEM are similar to those of SFEM. By combining the simplified model, IGFEM, a gradient-based optimization algorithm and sensitivity analysis, we obtain optimal parallel designs of the embedded micro-channel network that are substantial better than the reference designs both in

terms of the maximum temperature and the variance of the temperature field. While the optimal parallel design for low number of branches is characterized by vertically oriented interior channels to maximize area coverage, the optimal parallel design for high number of branches contains shorter diagonally oriented interior channels.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been supported by the Air Force Office of Scientific Research Multidisciplinary University Research Initiative (Grant No. FA9550-09-1-0686) and by the National Science Foundation Division of Civil, Mechanical and Manufacturing Innovation (Award No. 1436720).

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